

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

3 Mediterranean Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

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With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

[Seagrass Red List](#)

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Po *Posidonia oceanica*

Bioregion
3

- Key
- Leaves 40-50 cm
 - Leaf tip rounded
 - Rhizome robust, brush-like and fibrous
 - Flowers emerge on a stem
 - Monoecious

Flowering
Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
3

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

female
& male

Seedling

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zn *Nanozostera noltii*

Bioregion
3

- Key**
- Flat narrow leaves to 30 cm with open sheath
 - Leaf tip rounded and unevenly notched
 - Thin rhizome, shoots at each node
 - Flowers on branched stem
 - Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ankel et al 2021

Stage	Description
I	Yellow-green spathe, sheath closed; pistils and stamens are visible, aligned onto the stem
II	Pistils (IIa) and/or stamens erected (IIb); styles and stigma and/or anthers are outside the sheath
III	Stigma brown, start to depart from spathe; often with stamens already detached from the spathe
IV	Green spathe with immature seeds; sheath closed
V	Green/brown spathe, dark brown seeds are visible, sheath open

Cn *Cymodocea nodosa*

Bioregion
3

Key

- Flat leaves to 30 cm
- Leaf tip rounded, slightly serrated
- Rhizome robust with one root per node
- Flowers emerge from sheath
- Dioecious

Flowering
Parts

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion
3

- Key
- Paddle-shaped leaves
 - Leaf hairs on both sides
 - Leaf margins serrated
 - Leaves 1-4 cm long
 - Monoecious
 - Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male & female

fruit

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Invasive species

Bioregion
3

Key

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0 to 60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

Rc *Ruppia cirrhosa*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip, 25 cm long
- Fruits cluster on spiral stem
- Depth intertidal to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
3

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip with 2-3 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Global Seagrass Species References

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